

A new aliphatic ester from the aerial parts of *Polygonum polystachyum*

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A new aliphatic ester, pentacosanyl heptacosanoate was isolated from *Polygonum polystachyum* Wallich. alongwith five known compounds heptacosanoic acid, β -sitosterol, β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside, quercetin, quercetin-3-O-L-rhamnopyranoside. Structures of the isolated compounds were established by the application of spectroscopic techniques.

Polygonum species find wide application in medicinal science¹. Dried and crushed *P. polystachyum* Wallich. was extracted with ethanol and the results are reported as below.

Results and discussion

Compound **1**, m.p. 72–74^o; IR spectrum showed absorption bands at 1734, 731 and 720 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of carbonyl group and long aliphatic chain in the compound. EI-MS spectrum revealed [M]⁺ at *m/z* 760, corresponding to the molecular formula C₅₂H₁₀₄O₂. The peak at *m/z* 369 displayed the formation of alcoholic moiety due to cleavage of molecular ion at ester group site. ¹H NMR spectrum exhibited signals at δ 4.05 (2H, t), 1.62 (2H, m), 1.30 (2H, m), 1.28 (90H, m) showing the presence of 48 methylene groups. Signal at δ 2.3 (2H, t) corresponded to the α -CH₂ to -COO and at δ 0.9 (6H, t) indicated 2 methyl groups. ¹³C NMR (DEPT) spectrum suggested 2 methyl, 49 methylene and 1 quaternary-carbons. ¹³C NMR showed the characteristic signal for carbonyl carbon (δ 174.0) of an ester group. The structure of an ester was further confirmed by hydrolysis, which yielded acidic (**1a**) and alcoholic (**1b**) moieties.

Compound **1a**, EI-MS suggested the molecular weight 410. It gave no colour with TNM thereby indicating its saturated nature. ¹H NMR spectrum exhibited signals at δ 2.35 (2H, t), 1.62 (2H, m), 1.30 (2H, m), 1.28 (44H, m) showing the presence of 25 methylene groups. Signal at δ 2.35 (2H, t) corresponded to the α -CH₂ to -COOH and at δ 0.87 (3H, t) indicated a methyl group. ¹³C NMR (DEPT) spectrum suggested one methyl, 25 methylene and one quaternary-carbons. ¹³C NMR showed the characteristic signal for carboxylic acid at δ 179.6. Hence, **1a** must be *n*-heptacosanoic acid.

Compound **1b**, molecular formula was established as C₂₅H₅₂O on the basis of EI-MS *m/z* 368 [M]⁺. Other peaks appeared as an interval of 14 mass units i.e. by regular loss of -CH₂ group. A peak at *m/z* 149 (M-H₂O) was formed by loss of water. Its saturated nature was evidenced from the fact that it didnot produce colour with TNM². It gave positive test with ceric ammonium nitrate indicating alcoholic nature. The IR spectrum showed it to be a long chain primary alcohol, showing the usual absorption band at 3540 cm⁻¹ for free -OH group. C-O stretching vibration of a primary alcohol at 1062 cm⁻¹ and a doublet at 731 and 720 cm⁻¹ for a straight chain methylene group [(-CH₂-)_n (*n* > 4)]. ¹H NMR exhibited a triplet for 3 protons of methyl group at δ 0.9 and a broad signal with side bands, integrating for 46 protons of methylene groups at 1.25. A triplet at 4.05 for two protons (-O-CH₂) was observed and a broad signal at 3.7 accounted for one -OH group. Thus, the compound **1b** was characterized as pentacosanol.

From the above evidence, the structure of compound **1** was determined as pentacosanyl heptacosanoate.

Pentacosanyl heptacosanoate

Experimental

TLC was performed on silica gel using CHCl₃-MeOH-H₂O (64 : 32 : 10; lower layer) and the spots were detected with vanillin-H₂SO₄ followed by heating. Column chromatography was carried out on 60–120-mesh silica gel with light petroleum (60–80°C)-EtOH (98 : 2) as the eluent. EI-MS was recorded on JMS-SX102A 5890 series II spec-

trometer. IR spectra recorded on FTIR 8100 Shimadzu spectrophotometer. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL JNM-A600 spectrometer with TMS as an internal standard and chemical shifts were expressed in the δ (ppm) scale.

Plant material :

Aerial parts of *P. polystachyum* Wallich. were collected from Tungnath, Rudraprayag, Uttaranchal, India. Dried and powdered plant material (4 kg) was extracted with ethanol. The ethanol extract was then further partitioned in light petroleum (60–80°C). The petroleum extract (100 g) was column chromatographed over Si-gel using gradient elution with light petroleum-EtOH (98 : 2) afforded pentacosanyl heptacosanoate (2 g) **1** along with heptacosanoic acid **2**. The residue of petroleum free mass was chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh) and elution was carried out with chloroform and methanol (95 : 5) afforded, compound **3**, identified as β -sitosterol; **4**, identified as β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside; **5**, identified as quercetin and **6**; identified as quercetin-3-O-L-rhamnopyranoside.

Compound **1**, white amorphous powder, m.p. 72–74°C (uncorr.); IR (KBr) 1734 (C=O of ester), 3650 cm^{-1} (-OH); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 4.05 (2H, t), 2.3 (2H, t), 1.62 (2H, m), 1.3 (2H, m), 1.28 (90H, m), 0.9 (6H, t, J 7.02 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) 174.0 (-COOR), 64.3 (C-1'), 34.3 (C-2), 29.4 (C'-s-3'-24' and C-4-25), 28.6 (C-2'), 25.0 (C-3), 22.6 (C-26), 14.7 (C-25', C-27); EI-MS m/z : 760 $[\text{M}]^+$. 1.5 g of this compound was dissolved in 2 ml of purified chloroform and 1 ml of NaOEt. It was continuously stirred at room temperature, kept for 5–6 h and reaction was regularly monitored by TLC in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{-CHCl}_3$ (5 : 5) and then neutralized by dil. H_2SO_4 and concentrated. It was column chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh) using gradient elution with $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{-CHCl}_3$ (5 : 5) solvent system

afforded compound **1a** (6.5 mg) and compound **1b** (4 mg).

Compound **1a**, heptacosanoic acid, ($\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 2.35 (2H, t), 1.62 (2H, m), 1.30 (2H, m), 1.28 (44H, m), 0.87 (3H, t); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) 179.6 (-COOH), 34.3 (C-2), 29.4 (C-4-25), 25.0 (C-3), 22.6 (C-26), 14.7 (C-27); EI-MS m/z 410 $[\text{M}]^+$. **1b**, pentacosanol, ($\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}$), m.p. 62–64°C (uncorr.); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 4.05 (2H, t, J 6.71 Hz), 3.7 (1H, br s, OH), 1.25 (46H, m), 0.9 (3H, t, J 7.02 Hz); EI-MS m/z 368 $[\text{M}]^+$. Compound **2**, white needles, m.p. 135–137°C (uncorr.); IR (KBr) 1734, 2918, 2849, 1473, 731, 720 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 2.35 (2H, t, J 7.02 Hz), 1.62 (2H, m), 1.3 (2H, m), 1.25 (44H, m), 0.87 (3H, t, J 7.02 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz CDCl_3) δ 179.6 (-COOH), 35.16 (C-2), 30.4 (C-4-25), 26.14 (C-3), 24.08 (C-26), 15.47 (C-27); EI-MS m/z 410 $[\text{M}]^+$. Compound **3**, white needles, m.p. 135–137°C; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -48.0° ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$); IR (ν_{max} KBr) 3340, 2970, 2959, 2920, 1640, 1463 cm^{-1} ; EI-MS m/z 414 $[\text{M}]^+$ 398, 367, 351, 303, 273, 271, 255, 231, 229, 215, 189, 133, 105. Compound **4**, white crystals, m.p. 289–291°C; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -39°C ($c = 0.9$, pyridine); IR (ν_{max} KBr) 3400, 1640, 878 and 780 cm^{-1} . Compound **5**, yellow needles, m.p. 312–313°C; UV (λ_{max} MeOH, nm) 370, 301 (sh), 268, 225; EI-MS m/z 302 $[\text{M}]^+$, 301 (M-H), 285, 284, 273, 257, 229, 153, 137, 124, 109. Compound **6**, yellow needles, m.p. 180–184°C (Found : C, 59.01; H, 4.88. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_{11}$: C, 56.25; H, 4.63%); UV (λ_{max} MeOH, nm) 350, 301 (sh), 266 (sh) and 257.

References

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